

A Review on Environmental Impact of Pesticide Usage and Its Agronomic Management Strategies

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Abstract

The Sustainability and long-term welfare of farmers and lands depends on good quality water, soil, air and other natural resources available. Pesticides are crucial in agricultural production. This study provides an overview of negative effect of the pesticides on the environment, particularly when the pesticide escaped outside of the intended application area. The study clearly highlights the serious consequences of pesticide use on various environmental components and also ways to protect the environment by agronomic remedial practices. I intend to acknowledge that, there are some fine-tunings and adjustments are to be made to wean farmers from pesticide reliance. Also, Biopesticides should also be developed alongside synthetic pesticides to minimize farmers reliance on synthetic pesticides and the pollution caused in the environment. Subsequently, the environmental protection is a global concern, it is high time we need to understand the gravity of the situation and create awareness among the manufacturers, policy makers, government agencies, common men and farmers especially for safety pesticide handling and application.

Keywords: Agronomic practices, biopesticides, environmental impacts, pesticides

Introduction

Pesticides are crucial and one of the most important chemicals used in agricultural production. They have been used by farmers to control insects and weeds, and there have been reports of a remarkable increase in their use in agricultural products. The expansion in the total populace in the twentieth century could never have been conceivable without an equal expansion in food production. Tudi *et al.*, (2021) stated that around 33 percent of agricultural commodities are created relying upon the use of pesticides. There would be a 78 percent decline in fruit production, 54 percent decline in vegetable production, and a 32 percent decline in cereal production if pesticides were not used. However, the use of pesticides can also have negative effects on the environment, particularly if the pesticide is spread outside of the intended application area. Sharma *et al.*, (2019) reported that many procedures are influence what befalls pesticides in the ecosystem. These procedures incorporate adsorption, breakdown, degradation and transfer, that

incorporates processes that move the pesticide away from the intended site of the subjected area and spray drift, leaching, volatilization, runoff, crop removal and absorption are all reasons for main causes of pollution or non-target damage.

History and its classifications

The historical backdrop of pesticide use can be isolated into three timeframes (Tudi *et al.*, 2021). During the first-time frame before the 1870s, pests were constrained by utilizing different natural compounds. The first recorded utilization of insect sprays was around quite a while back by Sumerians. They utilized sulfur mixtures to control mites and insects. Pyrethrum is acquired from the dried blossoms of the *Chrysanthemum Cinerariaefolium*, "pyrethrum daisies", and has been utilized as an insecticide spray for more than 2000 years. During the subsequent period, somewhere in the range of 1870 and 1945, peoples started to utilize inorganic manufactured materials. The third time frame began after 1945, addressed by the utilization of engineered synthetic pesticides with the revelation of the impacts of aldrin, Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDT), endrin, β -Hexachlorocyclohexane (BHC), 2,4-D, dieldrin, parathion, chlordane, and captan. In present day agriculture, researchers are attempting to foster genetically engineered crops intended to deliver their own insect sprays or display protection from expansive range herbicide items or irritations. Gill and Garg, (2014) reported that pesticides are arranged by various order terms like functional groups, chemical classes, toxicity and modes of action. First and foremost, pesticides are arranged by various focuses of pests, including rodenticides, insecticides, fungicides and herbicides.

Pesticide use impact on environmental

Pesticides are utilized to kill harmful insects and control weeds as a component of their chemical compounds, in this manner, they can be poisonous to different organisms in the environment, including beneficial insects, fish, birds, and nontarget plants, as well as various ecological media, including crops, water, air, soil (Gill and Garg, 2014). Such chemical residue deposits influence human wellbeing through the climate and food defilement or contamination. In addition, pesticide defilement gets away from the target objective plants, bringing about ecological pollution. At the point when pesticides are applied to a target objective plant or discarded, they can possibly enter the ecological system. On entering the ecological system, pesticides can go through cycles like degradation and transfer (or movement). Pesticide degradation in the environment delivers new synthetics. Pesticides move from the objective site to other natural media or non-

target plants by move processes including leaching, spray drift, adsorption, runoff, and volatilization. The various kinds of synthetic compounds demonstrate their disparities in natural way of behaving (Tudi *et al.*, 2021).

Agronomic Management Practices

Combining pesticide use with agronomic management techniques, the application of typical agronomic techniques (solarization and bio solarization) to speed up the breakdown of these pesticide degradation of bifenthrin, tolclofos-methyl, and endosulfan in contaminated soil (Fenoll *et al.*, 2011). Models should better account for mulching, such as plastic, crop residues and related crops, as well as other cutting-edge techniques. The Root Zone Water Quality Model (RZWQM) models pretends pesticide interruption by mulch during application of pesticide (Mottes *et al.*, 2014).

Biopesticides

As a safer method to control pest populations such weeds, plant diseases, and insects while causing less damage to humans and the environment, biopesticides are generating interest on a worldwide basis. Biopesticides are efficient, biodegradable, and leave no environmental residues behind. As a promising alternative to chemical pesticides, the use of biopesticides as a supplement is becoming more and more popular throughout the world (Tijjani *et al.*, 2016). Kumar and Singh, (2015) reported that only 2% of plant protectants used globally now are biopesticides, but their growth rate has been on the rise over the past 20 years. Over 3,000 tons of biopesticides are thought to be produced year globally, and this number is rising quickly. Some of the major factors driving the biopesticide market include rising consumer demand for agricultural produce free of residues, a booming organic food industry, and easier registration than chemical pesticides. The usage of biopesticides is rising rapidly worldwide, at 10 percent a year.

Future research needs

As conclusion to control pesticide use, new systems and methods are required in surveying the impact of far and wide utilization of pesticides on environment and steps ought to be made to give awareness among public to limit the use of harmful risk pesticides. Yet the above discussion clearly highlights the serious consequences of pesticide use on various environmental components. Further studies focus on both industrial and environmental revelations and their related health risk evaluation of pesticides to more readily comprehend pesticide use and the executives later on. Regarding agronomic pesticide practices, there are fine-tuning and adjustments are needed to be

made to wean farmers from pesticide reliance. Also, Biopesticides should also be developed alongside synthetic pesticides to minimize pesticide pollution in the environment. Subsequently, the environmental protection is a global concern, we need to create an awareness and to convey the logical scientific results of the exposure and occupational and ecological wellbeing risk evaluations among the manufacturers, policy makers, government agencies, farmers, and the common men to for safety pesticide application, the avoidance of adverse human wellbeing impacts by improper pesticide utilization, and also switch-over to biopesticides for the pest management requirements.

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